

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

UNIVERSITÀ
DI TORINO

PRIVATE LAW IN THE ENERGY COMMONS A MULTIDISCIPLINARY CHALLENGE

CAMPUS LUIGI EINAUDI, TURIN, 27-28 MARCH 2024

This is the final conference of the project 'Private Law and the Energy Commons'. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101024836.

To attend, please, register [here](#)

TUESDAY 26 MARCH 2024

18h30 | CITY HIKE & DINNER (optional; for own account)

Meet in front of **Palazzo Reale** (Piazza Castello)

WEDNESDAY 27 MARCH 2024

08h30 - 09h00 | Registration

Venue: Sala Lauree blu, Campus Luigi Einaudi

Lungo Dora Siena, 100/A - Turin

OPENING | Welcome & Introduction

09h00 - 09h30

Introductions: **Björn Hoops** (Universities of Groningen and Turin)

Housekeeping: **Anna Grignani** (University of Eastern Piedmont)

Welcome: **Raffaele Caterina** (Director of the Department of Law, University of Turin)

Group 1

Energy Regulation and Regulatory Private Law for Energy Commons

Chair: **Francesco Costamagna** (University of Turin)

09h30 - 10h30

Maciej M. Sokołowski (Keio University, Japan)

Energy Communities: A Problem or a Solution for the Energy System in Transition? A Regulatory Riddle

Enrico Giarmanà (University of Catania)

The First Italian Transposition: Very Small-Scale Sharing

Matteo Caldera (Italian Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development, ENEA)

The Search for the Right Balance in the Italian Transposition

10h30 - 11h00 | Discussion

11h00 - 11h30 | TEA

Group 2

LEGAL FORMS I: Energy Commons in German and Italian Practice

Chair: **Michele Graziadei** (University of Turin)

11h30 - 12h30

Franz Nieper (energcity Erneuerbare GmbH, Leer)

Legal Forms of Renewable Energy Communities in Germany

Francesca Dealessi & Andrea Lanciani (Weigmann Studio Legale)

Obstacles to the Realisation of a Renewable Energy Community due to the (unnecessary?) complexity of European and national regulations

Francesco Dal Piaz (Dal Piaz Studio Legale)

Renewable Energy Communities in Italy: The Challenges of Public Governance

12h30 - 13h00 | Discussion

13h00 - 14h00 | LUNCH

Group 3

LEGAL FORMS II: Legal Forms for Energy Commons Compared

Chair: **Edoardo Ferrante** (University of Turin)

14h00 - 15h00

Jens Lowitzsch (Kelso Institute Europe & Viadrina University)

Meeting the Heterogeneity Challenge - Consumer Stock

Ownership Plans as the Prototype Business Model for Energy Communities

Ivan Libero Nocera (University of Bergamo)

Legal Forms for Energy Commons under the Codice Civile and Beyond

Björn Hoops (Universities of Groningen & Turin)

Notions of Community in Energy Democracy and Legal Forms

15h00 - 15h30 | Discussion

15h30 - 16h00 | TEA

Group 4

COMMUNITY AND PARTICIPATION: Conceptualizing the Commons

Chair: **Björn Hoops** (Universities of Groningen and Turin)

16h00 - 17h00

Lea Diestelmeier (University of Groningen)

Exploring Legal Frameworks for Communal Benefits of Energy Communities

Camila Vergara (University of Essex)

Anti-Oligarchic Energy Networks

Ugo Mattei (University of Turin, Hastings College)

Energy Poverty and the Commons

17h00 - 17h30 | Discussion

20h00 | Conference Dinner

Venue: Società Canottieri Armida, Viale Virgilio 45, Torino

<https://www.canottieriarmida.it>

THURSDAY 28 MARCH 2024

Group 5

COMMUNITY AND PARTICIPATION: The role of public bodies, inclusivity, and technological opportunities

Chair: **Lorna Fox O'Mahony** (University of Essex)

09h00 - 10h20

Gwen Savitz (University of Tulsa)

How Administrative Rules (Dis)incentivize Small-Scale Production

Alessandro Sciuillo (University of Turin)

The Role of REC in the Just Energy Transition Pathway

Anna Grignani (University of Eastern Piedmont)

The Role of the Public Administration in the Implementation of the Just Energy Transition

Daniel Crunkleton (University of Tulsa)

Using Artificial Intelligence to Optimize Energy Commons

10h20 - 11h00 | Discussion

11h00 - 11h30 | TEA

Group 6

SCALE I: Growth, Professionalization and Collaboration

Chair: **Franz Nieper** (energcity Erneuerbare GmbH, Leer)

11h30 - 12h30

Holger Klos (Bürgerenergiegenossenschaft Pfaffenhofen)

Success Factors of Sustainable Citizen Participation in Pfaffenhofen

Sara Gollessi (èNostra cooperative)

Upscaling and Evolution of Energy Democracy Initiatives in Italy:

Sharing Energy and Experiences

Peter Bloom (University of Essex)

Mobilizing the Commons: Upscaling Adaptable Sustainable Transitions

12h30 - 13h00 | Discussion

13h00 - 14h00 | LUNCH

Group 7

SCALE II: Energy Commons, Scale, and Resilient Property Theory

Chair: **Alessandra Quarta** (University of Turin)

14h00 - 15h00

Bram Akkermans (Maastricht University)

Normative Resilient Property Theory - Property Responses to Crises

Marc Roark (University of Tulsa)

Scale, Property Resources, and Resilience

Lorna Fox O'Mahony (University of Essex)

Understanding Energy Commons through Resilient Property Theory

15h00 - 15h30 | Discussion

15h30 - 16h00 | TEA

16h00 - 17h00

Roundtable: Insights on Energy Commons and Research Challenges

Marija Bartl (University of Amsterdam, EUI)

Peter Bloom (University of Essex)

Marat Karatayev (University of Turin)

Andrea Lanzini (Politecnico Torino)

Alessandra Quarta (University of Turin)

17h00 - 18h30 | APERITIVO

KIND ASSISTANCE FROM THE FOLLOWING INSTITUTIONS IS GREATFULLY ACKNOWLEDGED

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